

Guidance Document

Requirements Tool

This document aims at offering some support for the usage of the provided requirements tool for the purposes of testing a subset of the functionalities of the reactive links. Additional support can be provided per request, after contacting the authors of the research paper “Using Reactive Links to Propagate Changes Across Engineering Models” at the following email addresses:

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1. Setup required

The jar files provided were compiled using Java 1.8 and will likely require this same Java version to run. Additionally, the server runs on the 8080 port, so this port has to be open for the server to start.

We have only tested the executables in a setup with a Windows OS. For any struggles on running the components, please contact the authors for support.

More support on creating the links and the usage of the tool can be seen in the demonstration videos linked in the original paper. We do not have the rights to share the data used during the evaluation or any of the other plugins used.

2. The components of the replication package

The replication package contains three .jar files that are archived together. These three jar files are as follows:

- main-4.0.jar – the DesignSpace server
- value-linking-4.0-jar-with-dependencies.jar – the DesignSpace SDK, not needed for this replication
- RequirementsManagementTool-1.0-SNAPSHOT-jar-with-dependencies.jar – the Requirements Tool

The DesignSpace SDK can be used to create new custom plugins (see Plugin Guidance Document for more details), but it is not necessary for using the Requirements Tool.

3. Starting the DesignSpace server

All the communication between artifacts happens on the DesignSpace server. As such, this server has to be running at all times for the Requirements Tool to be used. If the server crashes, both the server and the tool have to be restarted.

The DesignSpace server can be started by running the jar file main-4.0.jar. We recommend using the command line, so that the server can be stopped at the end. In order to run the server, one has to execute the command:

```
java -jar main-4.0.jar
```

This command will initialize the server. Please wait until the server is fully started, marked by the line "Successfully initialized!".

4. Starting the Requirements Tool

Once the server is running, the tool can be started. In order to start the tool, the user has to execute the command:

```
java -jar RequirementsManagementTool-1.0-SNAPSHOT-jar-with-dependencies.jar
```

Unlike the server, this jar can also be run without the command line.

It must be noted that the Requirements Tool is a temporary research prototype and as such, it is not as robust as a commercial tool. One may notice warnings and caught errors in the command line during the run of the tool. These are almost exclusively UI issues coming from the use of SWT, and should not influence the reactive links functionality.

5. Connection to DesignSpace

Once the tool is running, a window will appear asking to connect to DesignSpace. We recommend creating a new workspace (which is the default option of the connection dialog) for a clean slate. However, if a workspace was already created, one can navigate the dropdown menu to identify their previous workspace. A new workspace can be named at creation for easier identification.

It must be noted that workspaces are not saved when the server is killed. As a result, one can only connect to an existing workspace during the same run of the server. We cannot provide a persistent version of the server as part of this replication package, but may be able to provide one per request or at a later date as part of an open-source version of DesignSpace.

6. Creating instances

As part of the Requirements Tool, the user can create components, categories and requirements. One can also create stakeholders and personas. It must be noted that stakeholders and personas were not tested for the linking functionalities, but other than unexpected UI issues, they should be usable as well.

The first step a user must take is to create a Component. This is the main mandatory field in creating a requirement, so it must exist first. For this, the user must click the left-most button of the user interface and a new window will open. In this new window, the user will find a template for the new component. The only mandatory field is the name. At the end, the user can save the component using the Save button at the bottom of the window (may need to be pressed twice due to an occasional UI error). The component may not yet be visible in the list, but should be selectable during the creation of the requirements.

Then, the user can optionally create a category to further classify the requirements. The categories are also automatically created when a new requirements is created, if they do not already exist.

Using the right-most button, the user can create a requirement. Similarly to the component, the button opens an empty template. Here, the user can insert the name of the requirement, and select the component (these being the only mandatory fields). The category field will search for an existing category with the same name or create a new one.

Another field of interest is the description. This is the field that was used during the evaluation. In the description, the user can specify custom properties using the following patterns:

`##propertyName=propertyValue##` or `##propertyName=propertyValue unit##`

The property value can be of any type (although if units are added, we recommend using floating point values). In order to create a string-typed property, the property value should be encased in quotation marks(""). A float-typed property is a numerical property containing a decimal point (e.g. 2.5, 3.0). An integer-typed property is a numerical property without a decimal point (e.g. 3). Boolean values can be expressed using true or false without quotation marks. Due to UI limitations, one cannot create collection-typed or reference-typed properties in the Requirements Tool prototype.

7. Creating reactive links

In order to create a reactive link, the user must select Links from the Tasks menu item above the main window. This will open a new window showing all the existing links (initially empty) and a button to add a new link. After selecting this button, a new window will allow the creation of a link.

The user must first select the instances and properties to be linked. For this, the user should select the instances from the two main lists on the window. When selecting an instance, the list below will be populated with all the properties of this instance. From this lower list, the user should select the property to be linked.

Then the user should select the operators to be applied. The dropdown menus on the upper part of the window allow the selection of the operators. The = operator represents value propagation/assignment. The other operators perform consistency checks. Please view Table 1 and Table 2 from the research article for further details on the meaning of each operator. In order to create unidirectional links, the operator can be left empty in the direction that is not considered.

The middle list allows the users to select where the link is stored within DesignSpace. This feature is of limited relevance for this prototype and is optional.

8. Limitations of the Requirements Tool prototype

As previously stated, the Requirements Tool is a research prototype and not meant for commercial use. There may be some GUI issues that were overlooked during our experiments or have appeared as a result of new versions of libraries. However, the main functionalities of the tool should be intact.

The major limitations to be considered are the following:

- Mixed-typed links are not handled well on the backend of the tool. As such, we recommend only linking between property values of the same type (e.g. avoid linking a value of 3 to a value

of 3.0). These links can be done if an operation is added to transform the types to a compatible configuration (e.g. one can link 3 to “3” if the operation toString() is added).

- Only the description was used during our experiments. As a result, while most properties can be used for propagation, the consistency checking is most visible in the description. An inconsistency in the description is marked with a yellow background.
- We do not recommend propagating the value of the component or category of the requirements. While it probably can be done, it may introduce issues in the functionality of the tool and UI.
- The custom properties in the description were only tested extensively for numerical values (as this was the only use case necessary in our evaluation scenarios). It seems that they struggle in some cases with correctly displaying the results of operators such as starts with.
- If errors are introduced that crash the tool and do not allow it to reconnect, we suggest creating a new workspace. In most cases, the workspaces are independent.
- If the GUI disappears from the screen, we suggest checking the open background windows. For reasons we have not been able to point out, SWT does not create a window in the taskbar consistently across different versions of the operating system. We have been unable to fix this issue.